

Trends in Pediatric Palliative Care Research (TPPCR) 2025; Issue #07: Commentary on

AlThaqafi, W. et al. and Sadler, K. et al.

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Abstract:

This TPPCR commentary discusses the 2025 papers by AlThaqafi, W. et al., Measuring the Level of Confidence and Identifying Gaps in Providing Palliative Care Services to Children by the Adult Palliative Care Team in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, Published in Journal of Palliative Medicine, and Sadler, K. et al., Intensity of Care at the End-of-Life in Pediatrics: A Single Center Analysis With Implications for Advanced Care Planning in Saudi Arabia, Published in Journal of Hospice and Palliative Care.

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One of the great pleasures of my career in medicine to date has been exposure to and learning from various world cultures - through patients, through medical travel, and from learners.

Through my time at McMaster, I have had the great pleasure of befriending, teaching, and learning from many medical trainees from Arab Gulf countries. Many of these trainees reported having had little formal education or past exposure to pediatric palliative care and expect little infrastructure to rely upon when going back home. This is why it brings me such delight to present two articles in this month's review from the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.

In the first, Sadler et al. report a descriptive retrospective study at a 1200-bed (adults and children) tertiary care centre in Riyadh over a 2-year period. The study characterized end-of-life care for 302 children. Cardiac disease was the most common underlying cause of death (30.1%) followed by malignancy (20.9%, of which over half were solid tumours). 80% had intensive interventions in the last 48 hours of life including CPR for 28%, and 75% died in the ICU. 67% had no advance care planning (defined as "agreement between the treating team and the child's legal guardians on priorities and goals of care if the child's condition deteriorates") while 67% had a DNAR order in place at the time of death, signed a median of 3 days before death (95% CI 1-15 days). Only 28% of the children who died had been referred to palliative care.

Next, Althaqafi et al. sought to understand the comfort of adult palliative care physicians in providing palliative care to children. The survey had 86 respondents, 84% of whom worked in tertiary hospitals. 67% had followed at least one child in the last year. 77% felt their training in pediatric palliative care was insufficient and while some were confident, many reported not feeling confident in pain management, communication, and care planning for children. A

majority preferred that pediatric palliative care operate as a separate service (78%).

These studies are invaluable in establishing the foundation for pediatric palliative care and defining targets for high-yield initiatives. It is a dangerous temptation to use published care models, benchmarks, outcomes, and guidelines from other contexts and attempt to apply them to one's own; however, the patients and families, their circumstances, their needs, and the available/potential healthcare supports may vary dramatically. For example, in comparison to my experiences here in North America, the high proportion of death by cardiac disease is notable, as are the proportion of solid tumours (generally behind CNS tumours and leukemias), the high degree of intensive care at end of life, and the limited advance care planning. As well, the responses from adult palliative care physicians and particularly the proportion of respondents working in tertiary care centres raises the question of access to confident care particularly outside of tertiary institutions.

When trainees come to Canada, my "role" has been to teach pediatric palliative care knowledge and skills, generally for them to take back to their country of origin. It is, however, abundantly clear that pediatric palliative care (and all health care for that matter) is inherently contextual; pediatric palliative care is intimately tied to ethics, culture, and law. Its practice requires translation – linguistically, yes – but also culturally, ethically, and legally. And so, we have found ourselves learning from one another, and not only for their future practice back home, but in the active care for Canadians in finding balance between culture and the Canadian medical, legal, and social system.

We all benefit from the development of pediatric palliative care expertise across the world, furthering our understanding of the application of its principles across the global spectrum of cultures, religions, health systems, and legislation.

Searching “Saudi Arabia” and “pediatric palliative care” in PubMed yields 8 search results – and all from within the past 2 years! I am thrilled to see this awakening of pediatric palliative care in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia and to know of great strides and cooperative efforts occurring across Arab Gulf countries (Alotaibi & Dighe, 2023; Alotaibi & Siden, 2023). For other areas of the world who may be starting a foundation of pediatric palliative care, the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia is demonstrating a measured, evidence-based approach to establishing a foundation upon which to flourish.

Additional References

1. Khan S, Sadler K, Siddiqui K, AlYami H, AlGarni M, Al-Kofide A, Podda A. [Physicians' Knowledge, Attitudes, and Perception Toward Pediatric Palliative Care in Saudi Arabia: A National Exploratory Survey.](#) *Palliat Med Rep.* 2023 Jul 21;4(1):185-192.
2. AlThaqafi W, Alqahtani BM, Khan MA, AlAbdulkarim AA, Alkhars AZ. [Demographic Data, Clinical Characteristics, and Outcomes of Pediatric Patients Who Received Palliative Care in King Abdullah Specialized Children's Hospital, Riyadh, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.](#) *Cureus.* 2023 Nov 18;15(11):e49032.
3. Sadler K, Khan S, AlGhamdi K, Alyami HH, Nancarrow L. [Addressing 10 Myths About Pediatric Palliative Care.](#) *Am J Hosp Palliat Care.* 2024 Feb;41(2):193-202.

4. Alotaibi Q, Dighe M. [Assessing the Need for Pediatric Palliative Care in the Six Arab Gulf Cooperation Council Countries.](#) *Palliat Med Rep.* 2023 Feb 16;4(1):36-40.
5. Alotaibi Q, Siden H. [An agenda to develop Pediatric Palliative care programs to serve children with life-threatening and life-limiting conditions in the Gulf Cooperation Council countries.](#) *Palliat Care Soc Pract.* 2023 Sep 29;17:26323524231201868